

This work has been financed by the Spanish State Research Agency (Agencia Española de Investigación, AEI) and the European Regional Development Fund (Fondo Europeo de Desarrollo Regional, FEDER) through the Research Project FEM2015-63912-P (AEI/FEDER, UE).

Sánchez-Prada, A., Delgado-Alvarez, C., Bosch-Fiol, E., & Ferrer-Perez, V. A. (2018). Implicit and Explicit Attitudes Toward Intimate Partner Violence Against Women: An Exploratory Study. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*. First published on line. doi: 10.1177/0886260518789903

Implicit and Explicit Attitudes towards Intimate Partner Violence against Women: An Exploratory Study.

For Peer Review

Introduction

Physical and sexual violence is a social and public health problem of epidemic proportions, which affects more than one third of all women globally (DeVries et al., 2013; FRA, 2014; Stockl et al., 2013). One of the most common forms of violence targeting women is perpetrated by a current or former intimate partner (Ellsberg, Jansen, Watts, & Garcia-Moreno, 2008; Garcia-Moreno, Jansen, Ellsberg, Heise, & Watts, 2006), referred to as intimate partner violence against women (IPVAW, Gracia, Rodriguez, & Lila, 2015; Martin-Fernandez, Gracia, Marco, Vargas, Santirso, & Lila, 2018; Rodriguez & Khalil, 2017; Uthman, Moradi, & Lawoko, 2010, 2011).

Previous research has shown that attitudes can be important predictors of behaviour (Glasman & Albarracin, 2006), and more specifically, important determinants of a variety of violent behaviours. When it comes to IPVAW, there is consistent evidence of three important implications of attitudes relating to this violence (Flood & Pease, 2009; Gracia & Lila, 2015; Gracia & Tomás, 2014; Gracia et al., 2015; Heise & Kotsdam, 2015; Wang, 2016): a) Attitudes have a fundamental and a causal relationship to the perpetration of violence against women. Specifically, there is a consistent relationship between men's adherence to sexist, patriarchal and sexually hostile attitudes and their use of this violence (Capaldi, Knoble, Shortt, & Kim, 2012; Fulu, Jewkes & Garcia-Moreno, 2013; Jewkes, Flood, & Lang, 2015; Puente, Ubillos, Echeburua, & Paez, 2016). b) Women's responses to this victimization (to blame themselves for the assault, to report it to the police, to experience negative psychological and emotional effects) are shaped by their own attitudes (Harris, Firestone, & Vega, 2005; Puente et al., 2016) and those of others around them (Kingsnorth & MacIntosh, 2004). And c) Attitudes play a role in the formal and informal responses to IPVAW adopted by family members, friends or professionals (Gracia, Garcia, & Lila, 2014). In fact, attitudes and responses regarding this violence play a role in shaping the social climate in which the violence occurs, a social climate that can contribute to either perpetuating or reducing the levels of violence in the society (Flood & Pease, 2009; Gracia et al., 2015). In summary, a social environment that accepts or even supports this violence in some circumstances contributes to creating a climate of tolerance that

1
2
3 makes it easier for perpetrators to persist in their violent behaviour, and makes it more difficult for
4
5 female victims to report the violence they suffer.

6
7 Two different approaches have been used to generally assess attitudes (Gawronski & Bodenhausen,
8
9 2006). Firstly, prior research has assessed attitudes with traditional methods, such as self-reports.
10
11 The success of these methods is partly due to their ease of administration, cost-effectiveness and
12
13 ability to provide rich sources of information for attitudes that are frequently referenced by an
14
15 individual (Paulhus & Vazire, 2007). However, given that explicit self-report methods are prone to
16
17 socially desirable responding, it is plausible that an effect derived from responses to self-report
18
19 measures may underrepresent the relationship between attitudes and behaviour (Fazio & Olson,
20
21 2003; Nosek, 2005; Ryan, 2013; Scott & Straus, 2007), supporting the need for alternative methods
22
23 of attitude assessment. For this reason, and to counteract this situation, some researchers have used
24
25 implicit methods of assessment. While explicit methods require a direct response to an item on a
26
27 questionnaire, implicit methods measure attitudes at an indirect level and provide another way to
28
29 index attitudes related to specific behaviours. However, the issue of congruency or non-congruency
30
31 of implicit and explicit measures is highly complex, and is considered differently in diverse
32
33 theoretical approaches. Moreover, research has, in general, found minimal relationships between
34
35 both types of measures (Echebarría, 2013; Fazio & Olson, 2003).

36
37 The implicit measures of attitudes, and IAT in particular, have emerged dramatically over the last
38
39 decade and been applied to several areas of social cognition (Payne & Gawronski, 2010). The Implicit
40
41 Association Test (IAT, Greenwald, McGhee, & Schwartz, 1998) is a latency-based computer task that
42
43 pairs a bipolar target category (e.g., violence vs. nonviolence) with a bipolar evaluative attribute
44
45 (e.g., negative vs. positive) on the same keystroke over the course of many trials. The fundamental
46
47 principle is that when two concepts that are strongly associated (e.g., “violence” and “negative”)
48
49 share the same key, the reaction time is less than when this is not the case (e.g., “violence” and
50
51 “positive”). In summary, the IAT is a measure of implicit cognition that assesses the strength of
52
53 cognitive associations by comparing reaction times to different pairings of concepts. It is also
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 considered a valid measure of implicit processing in that the psychological attributes of the
4 individual are inferred from the speed with which the participants respond to stimuli in the
5 categorization task (De Houwer, Teige-Mocigemba, Spruyt, & Moors, 2009).
6
7

8
9 These implicit measures, such as the IAT, have been used to assess attitudes and to try to predict
10 violent behaviours in different types of violence, such as rape (Süssenbach, Albrecht, & Böhner,
11 2017), sexualized violence (Larue, Schmidt, Imhoff, Eggers, Schönbrodt, & Banse, 2014), or dating
12 violence (Lee, Begun, DePrince, & Chu, 2016) and among different violent perpetrators (Bluemke,
13 Crombach, Hecker, Schalinski, Elbert, & Weierstall, 2017; Simane-Vigante, Plotka, & Blumenau,
14 2015). In addition, they have been used to predict treatment outcomes in sexual and intimate
15 partner offenders (Eckhardt & Crane, 2014).
16
17

18
19 In terms of IPVAW, researchers have typically measured attitudes with explicit measures by having
20 people complete self-report questionnaires (Gracia & Lila, 2015; Gracia et al., 2015), while only a few
21 studies have used IAT measures to assess attitudes towards intimate partner violence. For instance,
22 Robertson and Murachver (2007) examined offenders' attitudes towards violence using an IAT
23 measure in a sample of 39 participants incarcerated for intimate partner violence, as well as 133
24 non-incarcerated participants who served as a comparison group. The incarcerated sample had
25 significantly more positive attitudes towards violence, measured by IAT. However, the attitudes in
26 both sample groups towards violence were more similar when measured explicitly. In fact, one of
27 their conclusions was that the disparity between measures exemplified the need to include implicit
28 measures when assessing attitudes that are not publicly accepted. In a sample of 50 men from an
29 IPVAW intervention program and 40 non-violent men from the community used as a comparison,
30 Eckhardt, Samper, Suhr, and Holtzworth-Munroe (2012) obtained similar results by using three IAT
31 measures to examine attitudes towards women, violence and the associations between gender and
32 violence. They found that offenders had significantly more positive attitudes towards violence,
33 measured by IAT, as well as stronger associations between women and violence. In contrast, no
34 significant differences were found between samples on the self-report attitudes measurement.
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 These authors suggest that self-report measures to assess violence-related attitudes among IPVAW
4 offenders are limited by their tendency to defend themselves, to deny or minimize their violent
5 behaviour and to disguise their inclination to use violence. In a Spanish context, IAT has been used in
6 some research by Cantera et al. (Cantera & Blanch, 2010; Cantera & Gamero, 2012) to assess the
7 degree of social attachment of certain stereotypes about gender (men as providers and females as
8 caregivers) and violence (violent men, peaceful women), framed in the context of a debate on the
9 extent and limits of a gender approach when it comes to understanding and preventing intimate
10 partner violence. More recently, Gracia et al. (2015) developed a new analogue visual task assessing
11 acceptability of physical violence towards women in intimate relationships and observed that
12 perpetrators scored significantly higher in this acceptability than undergraduate students.
13
14 In short, most studies examining the predictive validity of measures for public attitudes towards
15 IPVAW have not included both implicit and explicit measures jointly. Consequently, the general
16 objective of our research is to provide multi-method measures for public attitudes towards IPVAW
17 (explicit and implicit). In order to achieve this goal, the first step would be to have a valid and
18 reliable measurement tool. Our hypothesis is that these implicit measures, neutralizing the effects of
19 social desirability and the response control of the subjects, will allow for more adequate
20 assessments. This paper presents preliminary results obtained in a pilot study from the designed
21 multi-method measures.
22
23

24 It is important to note that in the Spanish context, IPVAW is deemed gender violence (see Ferrer &
25 Bosch, 2014). Accordingly, the preamble to the Act on Comprehensive Protection Measures against
26 Gender Violence (Organic Act 1/2004 dated 28 December) points out that IPVAW is a social problem
27 and a form of gender – based violence. Additionally, and unlike what occurs in other international
28 contexts, gender violence is limited to acts perpetrated by men against women in an intimate
29 relationship (i.e., it calls gender violence to IPVAW). Although the decision to use this name gave rise
30 to a major controversy in Spain (Puleo, 2008), it has been maintained ever since. In line with this
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

practice, our experimental work uses the term gender violence to refer to IPVAV and to define the target category of the designed IAT.

Method

Participants

An opportunity sample of 190 Psychology undergraduates from two Spanish universities took part in this study: 32 men (18.8%) and 158 women (83.2%), with an average age of 20.01 years (SD=4.41; Range: 18-30). Of these, 60.5% studied some topic related to IPVAV and 55.3% participated in at least one non-curricular activity related to IPVAV. 93 participants (48.9%) reported that they had a partner, and 96 (50.5%) had no partner.

Measures

The *Inventory of Distorted Thoughts about Women and Violence* (IPDMV in the Spanish acronym, Echeburua & Fernandez-Montalvo, 1998; adapted version of Ferrer, Bosch, Ramis, Torrens, & Navarro, 2006) comprises 24 items, with a four-point response scale and four dimensions: *the inferiority of women compared to men* (7-items, $\alpha=.88$); *blaming female victims of abuse* (8-items, $\alpha=.66$); *violence as an appropriate problem-solving strategy* (5-items, $\alpha=.70$); and *minimization of IPVAV as a problem and exoneration of the abuser* (4-items, $\alpha=.52$). Higher scores indicate higher levels of distorted thoughts.

The *Inventory of Beliefs about Wife Beating* (IBWB, Saunders, Lynch, Grayson, & Linz, 1987; Spanish version of Expósito & Ruiz, 2010) is a 30-item self-report scale designed to assess participants' explicit attitudes towards wife beating, which comprises five dimensions: *wife beating is justified* (12-items, $\alpha=.86$); *wife gains from beating* (7-items, $\alpha=.78$); *help should be given* (5-items, $\alpha=.73$); *offender should be punished* (3-items, $\alpha=.61$), and *offender is responsible* (4-items, $\alpha=.62$). Some of these sub-scales have been recently used in Spanish populations with similar psychometric indicators (e.g., Gracia et al., 2015; Valor-Segura, Expósito, Moya, & López, 2014). The response format was adapted into a four-point scale with scores from the latter three dimensions being reversed so that higher scores indicate a greater justification of abuse.

1
2
3 In spite of the relatively low reliability of some of the above mentioned subscales (and, particularly,
4 in the *minimization of IPVAV as a problem and exoneration of the abuser* IPDMV's scale), they can
5 be considered appropriate enough for the purpose of the present study because even values around
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

The *Gender Violence Implicit Association Test* (GV-IAT, AUTHOR1) is a form of personalized IAT (the GV-IAT), used as an implicit measure of public attitudes towards IPVAV. The target categories were *Gender Violence vs. Non-Gender Violence*, and the attribute categories were *Good vs. Bad*. Six words from each of the aforementioned categories were used as stimuli: a) Attack, Force, Humiliate, Hit, Torture and Infringe for the category Gender Violence; b) Support, Collaborate, Cooperate, Empathize, Respect and Tolerate for the category Non-Gender Violence; c) Wonderful, Excellent, Phenomenal, Best, Positive and Optimum for the category Good; d) Horrible, Terrible, Disastrous, Worst, Negative and Appalling for the category Bad. Stimuli were displayed on a 20-inch screen with a PC running OpenSesame v.3.1.6 (Mathôt, Schreij, & Theeuwes, 2012) on Windows 8. Participants completed the GV-IAT task in seven blocks (Greenwald, Nosek, & Banaji, 2003), from which three were considered practice trials (B1-B2 included 24 trials; B5 included 48 trials), and four were the critical blocks (B3-B6 included 24 trials; B4-B7 included 48 trials).

Procedure

The study was approved by the Bioethics Committee of one of the participating universities and experimental sessions took place in the labs at each university. Upon arrival, participants were asked to read over the study description and consent form. After providing their informed consent to voluntary participation in the study, the participants completed the IAT and, thereafter, the two questionnaires.

During the IAT blocks, stimuli were presented in the middle of the screen with a black background. In each trial participants had to press a computer key (left or right) as quickly as possible to sort the stimulus into one of the two (target or attribute) categories displayed on the left and right side of

1
2
3 the screen. The presentation order for stimuli was randomly controlled across participants, and the
4
5 position on the screen of target categories was counterbalanced (half times left; half times right).
6
7 For exploratory purposes, according to the literature review, two frequently used IAT procedures
8
9 were tested (Nosek, Bar-Anan, Sriram, Jordan, & Greenwald, 2014; Nosek, Greenwald, & Banaji,
10
11 2007): the typical IAT procedure (with feedback), and the personalized IAT procedure (without
12
13 feedback). The typical IAT procedure (Greenwald et al., 1998) includes the provision of immediate
14
15 feedback when the participant has made an error (at which point the user is forced to enter the
16
17 correct choice before advancing to the next trial). This feedback might suggest that there is a
18
19 normatively correct response (Fazio & Olson, 2004). These factors might increase the accessibility of
20
21 normative information relevant to solving the mapping problem posed by the IAT, leaving attitudes
22
23 as only one of several potential types of associations that influence performance on the mapping
24
25 tasks. For these reasons, Olson and Fazio (2004) developed a personalized IAT, which among
26
27 different characteristics did not include error feedback (participants did not receive feedback, and
28
29 the IAT went on, even after an erroneous response, with no correction required). Participants were
30
31 randomly assigned to one of these two IAT conditions: 79 women and 10 men to the condition *with*
32
33 *feedback*; and 79 women and 22 men to the condition *without feedback*.
34
35

36 **D-scores Algorithm**

37
38 The fundamental principle of the IAT is that the reaction time (RT) is less when two concepts are
39
40 strongly associated than when this is not the case. Based on those response latencies, Greenwald et
41
42 al. (2003) proposed the *D-score* as an estimate of the IAT-effect, whose interpretation is similar to
43
44 Cohen's *d*. The optimization of reliability and validity of this algorithm has received much attention
45
46 in IAT research (e.g. Blanton, Jaccard, & Burrows, 2015; Fazio & Olson, 2003; Glashouwer, Smulders,
47
48 de Jong, Roefs, & Wiers, 2013; Greenwald et al., 2003; Nosek et al., 2014; Nosek et al., 2007). Taking
49
50 into account the authors' recommendations, D scores were calculated as follows:
51
52

- 53 "(1) use data from Blocks 3, 4, 6, and 7; (2) eliminate trials with latencies >10,000
54
55 ms; (3) eliminate subjects for whom more than 10% of trials have latencies <300
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 ms; (4) compute one standard deviation for all trials in Blocks 3 and 6, and another
4
5 standard deviation for all trials in Blocks 4 and 7; (5) compute means for trials in
6
7 each of the four blocks (Blocks 3, 4, 6, 7); (6) compute two difference scores (one
8
9 between 3 and 6 and the other between 4 and 7), subtracting what is intended to
10
11 represent the high (positive) end of the measure from the block containing
12
13 associations representing the low end; (7) divide each difference score by its
14
15 associated standard deviation from Step 4; and (8) average the two quotients from
16
17 Step 7". (Nosek et al., 2007, p. 273).

19 Regarding the topic of error latencies treatment, a deeply discussed issue in the IAT literature, two
20
21 procedures recommended in the literature were implemented for exploratory purposes: a) replacing
22
23 each error latency with the mean of correct latencies for the respective block, adding a 600
24
25 millisecond error penalty (Nosek et al., 2007); and b) integrating a 'built-in penalty' in error latencies
26
27 by computing the accumulated time of the wrong response and the time spent in correcting that
28
29 first response (Greenwald et al., 2003; Nosek et al., 2014; Richetin, Costantini, Perugini, &
30
31 Schönbrodt, 2015). The first procedure was applied to IATs both with and without feedback; the
32
33 latter, as per its definition, was applicable only to the condition *with feedback*.
34
35

36 Results

37 Implicit measures

38
39 Positive D-scores in GV-IAT indicates implicit rejection of gender violence: the higher the values, the
40
41 stronger the rejection (AUTHOR 1). According to the scores obtained in the two IAT procedures
42
43 tested (*without feedback* and *with feedback*), the former being calculated by the two algorithms
44
45 tested (*error penalty* and *built-in error penalty*), participants were classified into four levels of
46
47 rejection, according to D-intervals highlighted by collaborators of the Harvard Project Implicit (Ayala
48
49 & Martinez, 2013) (see Table 1).
50
51
52

53 Insert Table 1 here
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 The results obtained showed that the classification by categories varies according to the IAT
4 application condition (*without feedback* vs. *with feedback*), but not according to the D-scores
5 algorithm used. In the condition *without feedback*, the strong IAT effect (54.4% of participants
6 showing *strong rejection*) was overestimated compared to the condition *with feedback*, which
7 provided similar distributions to both algorithms. These results coincide in “*using the IAT, in which*
8 *respondents are not required to correct errors, is not recommended practice*” (Nosek et al., 2014,
9 p.18). Therefore, these results provide evidence of the best way to apply the GV-IAT. Consequently,
10 the comparisons between implicit and explicit measures were performed using D-scores from the
11 condition *with feedback*, including built-in error penalty – the most recommended procedure to
12 maximize validity (Greenwald et al., 2003).
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22

23 **Explicit measures vs implicit measures**

24
25 In order to classify participants by their explicit rejection of gender violence, four categories were
26 established: scores ≤ 2 (disagreement) were categorized as strong rejection; scores between 2 and
27 2.5 (near-disagreement) as moderate rejection; scores between 2.5 and 3 (near-agreement) as mild
28 rejection; and scores ≥ 3 (agreement) as null rejection.
29
30
31
32
33

34 Insert Table 2 and Table 3 here

35
36 The explicit measures yielded high percentages of strong rejection, except in the IBWB dimension
37 *offender is (not) responsible* (Table 2; 40.4%), and in the IPDMV dimension *minimizing violence and*
38 *exoneration of the abuser* (Table 3; 29.2%). These measures described a sample with a strong explicit
39 rejection of gender violence (88.8% of respondents in the IPDMV; 96.3% in the IBWB). In contrast,
40 the implicit measure reduced strong rejection to 36%.
41
42
43
44
45
46

47 The Chi square test shows no significant relationship between the participants' classification by
48 implicit measures and their classification by explicit measures, as shown in Table 4. The
49 independence between the implicit and explicit dimensions evaluated suggests that they are
50 different constructs (Nosek & Smyth, 2007; Nosek et al., 2014).
51
52
53
54

55 Insert Table 4 here

1
2
3 Focusing only on the sample segment with strong explicit rejection to IPVAW (79 of a sample of 82
4 when the rejection is measured by IPDMV; and 77 of a sample of 79 when it is measured by IBWB),
5
6 Figure 1 shows that the distribution to the implicit rejection for these two subsamples is identical in
7
8 both cases: null in 2.5% (n=2 in IPDMV and IBWB); mild in 16.5% (n=13 in IPDMV and IBWB);
9
10 moderate in about 42% (n=33 in IPDMV, and n=32 in IBWB), and strong only in about 39% (n=31 in
11
12 IPDMV, and n=30 in IBWB).
13
14

15
16 Insert Figure 1 here
17

18 **Differences by sex, knowledge, and activities**

19
20 The effect of sex, previous knowledge about IPVAW and participation in extracurricular activities
21
22 related to IPVAW were analysed using the nonparametric Mann-Whitney U test for independent
23
24 samples, due to the small size of some groups. Table 5 shows that the variables sex and participation
25
26 in extracurricular activities have no significant effects, in either the implicit or the explicit measures,
27
28 while the variable previous knowledge about IPVAW has a significant effect only in one explicit
29
30 measure (the help should (not) be given IBWB's scale).
31

32
33 Insert Table 5 here
34

35 **Discussion**

36
37 The study of attitudes towards IPVAW is a popular topic that has been widely researched. Implicit
38
39 assessment methodologies (e.g., the IAT) have been developed because explicit attitudes have been
40
41 deemed highly sensitive to the effects of social desirability (Nosek, 2005). In particular, IAT is
42
43 considered a valid measure of implicit processing in the sense that the psychological attributes of
44
45 the individual are inferred from the speed at which the participants respond to stimuli in the
46
47 categorization task.

48
49 In this context, the aim of this research is to contribute in the application of a form of personalized
50
51 IAT (the GV-IAT) to the study of public attitudes towards IPVAW. The results of this pilot study
52
53 achieved the objectives set out: first, they provide evidence on the best condition for applying GV-
54
55 IAT (with feedback) and the best procedure for estimating the IAT effect (built-in error penalty); in
56
57

1
2
3 addition, these findings are consistent with previous research on implicit measures of attitudes
4 towards IPVAV (i.e., Eckhardt & Crane, 2014; Gracia, et al., 2015; Robertson & Murachver, 2007).
5
6 Similarly, we observed a significant disparity between explicit and implicit measures of these
7 attitudes. In this vein, our results provide conclusive evidence of the need to incorporate implicit
8 measures in research into this social problem, and an encouraging proposal of a tool to assess them.
9
10 With regard to the sense of the observed disparity, although a very large majority of the sample
11 studied shows an explicit rejection of IPVAV (between 88.8% and 96.3%, according to the self-
12 report used), the proportion of rejection reduces to just under half when it is measured implicitly.
13
14 Researchers such as Echebarria (2013) suggest that the low correspondence between implicit and
15 explicit measures of attitudes may be due to methodological factors. Specifically, it could be
16 explained by a question of structural-fit, since the demands placed on the respondents by both types
17 of measures are entirely different. The Motivation and Opportunity as Determinants (MODE)
18 theoretical model (Fazio, 1990; Olson & Fazio, 2009) supports this reasoning, proposing the
19 existence of a single-attitude construct (Bohner & Dickel, 2011) which can manifest as behaviour
20 through spontaneous or deliberative processes. This model seeks to explain when there is a
21 correspondence between attitudes and behaviours, and when there is not; it suggests that the
22 consistency of attitudes and behaviours depends on processing capacities and motivation, and
23 proposes that attitudes are only one of the various determinants of behaviours. The presence of
24 other factors such as social norms against the expression of certain opinions (e.g., tolerance to
25 IPVAV), the desire to project a specific self-image, the need to be accepted by others, and the
26 amount of personal experience with a particular domain, etc. also contribute to shaping behaviours.
27
28 In these situations (prototypical context of explicit measures), MODE predicts a low correspondence
29 between attitudes and behaviours, since the situational forces are strong enough to inhibit the
30 expression of attitudes. In other situations (as well as the prototypical context of implicit measures),
31 there are no constraints on the overt expression of attitudes (ambiguity, presence of others with
32 similar attitudes, noncontroversial topics etc.), and there is a stronger correspondence between
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 attitudes and behaviours (Greenwald, Poehlman, Uhlmann, & Banaji, 2009; Nosek, 2005; Nosek,
4 Banaji, & Greenwald, 2002). In short, one could argue that implicit measures are generally unbiased
5 by motivational influences, whereas explicit self-reports are often influenced by social desirability
6 concerns (Fazio & Olson, 2003; Nosek, 2005).
7

8
9
10
11 Another important point to note is that previous studies have frequently indicated several factors
12 influencing attitudes towards IPVAV including age, gender, education, residency, economic status,
13 or patriarchal gender role (Gracia & Lila, 2015). For instance, some surveys and reviews in
14 developing countries have suggested that men are more likely than women to approve of
15 behaviours associated with IPVAV (Ferrer & Bosch, 2014; Flood & Pease, 2009), and that younger
16 people tend to justify IPVAV more often than their elders (Waltermauer (2012). Wang (2016)
17 reviews these factors and concludes that education might be the most crucial factor and may
18 decrease the risk of accepting or justifying IPVAV.
19

20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28 The results of this study show that variables as sex, previous knowledge about IPVAV, or
29 involvement in IPVAV-related activities do not have a significant effect on either implicit or explicit
30 measures of attitudes towards IPVAV (only the variable previous knowledge has some effect in the
31 *help should (not) be given* in the IBWB scale). However, the sample studied is highly homogeneous
32 (made up exclusively of undergraduates, most of them women and young). This homogeneity is
33 precisely one of the limitations of this work. It is therefore necessary to continue working with
34 broader and much more diverse samples (in terms of their composition by sex, age, level of
35 education, status, etc., and, particularly, in terms of a broader sample of men) to obtain more
36 conclusive results. Other limitations include: the absence of broader psychometric evidence on the
37 Spanish use of IBWB; the narrow reliability of the minimization of IPVAV as a problem and
38 exoneration of the abuser in the IPDMV scale and the offender is responsible in the IBWB scale; and
39 the need of an in-depth discussion on the best algorithm for calculating D-scores, as well as their
40 interpretation. Further research should address all of these limitations.
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 As we stated earlier, the majority of research about IPAWE attitudes and the factors influencing them
4 has used explicit measures (Gracia & Lila, 2015; Gracia et al., 2015). Nevertheless, given the potential
5 biases and risks associated with using explicit attitude measures, this assessment may not be
6 completely accurate (Fazio & Olson, 2003; Gracia et al., 2015; Nosek, 2005). The combined use of
7 explicit and implicit attitude assessment could potentially lead to a more accurate measurement of
8 attitudes towards IPVAW. Moreover, and in spite of their limitations, the current preliminary
9 findings contribute to the body of literature by providing conclusive information on the need to
10 incorporate implicit measures of IPVAW attitudes into research on this important social problem. In
11 fact, the use of implicit measures to assess attitudes may provide new assessment approaches and a
12 step forward in the study of attitudes toward IPVAW in community samples, professionals, victims
13 and also perpetrators. Particularly, the use of these implicit measures in batterer intervention
14 programs, which may be more sensitive than self-reported measures that are susceptible to social
15 desirability, may provide new assessment tools for treatment providers (Gracia et al., 2015; Martin-
16 Fernandez et al., 2018).

References

AUTHOR 1

Ayala, A., & Martinez, D. (2013). Análisis de los resultados del Test de Asociación Implícita de la
elección presidencial mexicana de 2012. *Justicia Electoral*, 1(12), 59-99.

Blanton, H., Jaccard, J., & Burrows, C. N. (2015). Implications of the Implicit Association Test D-
transformation for psychological assessment. *Assessment*, 22(4), 429-440. doi:
10.1177/1073191114551382

Bluemke, M., Crombach, A., Hecker, T., Schalinski, I., Elbert, T., & Weierstall, R. (2017). Is the Implicit
Association Test for aggressive attitudes a measure for attraction to violence or
traumatization? *Zeitschrift fur Psychologie/Journal of Psychology*, 225(1), 54-63. doi:
10.1027/2151-2604/a000281

- 1
2
3 Bohner, G., & Dickel, N. (2011). Attitudes and attitude change. *Annual Review of Psychology*, *62*,
4
5 391-417. doi: 10.1146/annurev.psych.121208.131609
6
- 7 Cantera, L. M., & Blanch, J. M. (2010). Percepción Social de la Violencia en la Pareja desde los
8
9 Estereotipos de Género Social. *Psychosocial Intervention*, *19*(2), 121–127. doi:
10
11 10.593/in2010v19n2a3
12
- 13 Cantera, L., & Gamero, V. (2012). Nuevas metodologías en investigación y prevención de la violencia
14
15 en la pareja. *Global Journal of Community Psychology Practice*, *3*(4).
16
- 17 Capaldi, D. M., Knoble, N. B., Shortt, J. W., & Kim, H. K. (2012). A systematic review of risk factors for
18
19 intimate partner violence. *Partner Abuse*, *3*(2), 231-280. doi: 10.1891/1946-6560.3.2.231
20
- 21 De Houwer, J., Teige-Mocigemba, S., Spruyt, A., & Moors, A. (2009). Implicit measures: A normative
22
23 analysis and review. *Psychological Bulletin*, *135*, 347-368. doi: 10.1037/a0014211
24
- 25 Devries, K. M., Mak, J. Y. T., Garcia-Moreno, C., Petzold, M., Child, J. C., Felder, G., Lim, S., Bacchus, L.
26
27 J., Engell, R. E., Rosenfeld, L., Pallito, C., Vos, T., Abrahams, N., & Watts, C. H. (2013). The
28
29 global prevalence of intimate partner violence against women. *Science*, *340*, 1527-1528. doi:
30
31 10.1126/science.1240937
32
- 33 Echebarría, E. (2013). Research reports relationship between implicit and explicit measures of
34
35 attitudes: The impact of application conditions. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, *9*(2). doi:
36
37 10.5964/ejop.v9i2.544
38
- 39 Echeburua, E., & Fernandez-Montalvo, J. (1998). Hombres maltratadores. In E. Echeburua & P. Corral
40
41 (Eds.), *Manual de violencia familiar* (pp. 71-175). Madrid: Siglo XXI.
42
- 43 Eckhardt, C. I., & Crane, C. A. (2014). Male perpetrators of intimate partner violence and implicit
44
45 attitudes toward violence: associations with treatment outcomes. *Cognitive Therapy &*
46
47 *Research*, *38*(3), 291-301. doi:10.1007/s10608-013-9593-5
48
- 49 Eckhardt, C. I., Samper, R., Suhr, L., & Holtzworth-Munroe, A. (2012). Implicit attitudes toward
50
51 violence among male perpetrators of intimate partner violence: A preliminary investigation.
52
53 *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, *27*(3), 471-491. doi: 10.1177/0886260511421677.
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 Ellsberg, M., Jansen, H. A., Heise, L., Watts, C. H., & Garcia-Moreno, C. (2008). WHO Multi-country
4 Study on Women's Health and Domestic Violence against Women Study Team. *Lancet*,
5 371(9619), 1165-72.
6
7
8
- 9 Expósito, F., & Ruiz, S. (2010). Reeducción de maltratadores: una experiencia de intervención desde
10 la perspectiva de género. *Psychosocial Intervention*, 19(2), 145-151. doi:
11 10.5093/in2010v19n2a6
12
13
14
- 15 Fazio, R. H. (1990). Multiple processes by which attitudes guide behavior: The MODE model as an
16 integrative framework. In M. P. Zanna (Ed.), *Advances in experimental social psychology* (Vol.
17 23, pp. 75–109). San Diego, CA: Academic Press.
18
19
20
- 21 Fazio, R. H., & Olson, M. A. (2003). Implicit measures in social cognition. *Annual Reviews Psychology*,
22 54, 297–327.
23
24
25
- 26 Ferrer, V. A., & Bosch, E. (2014). Gender violence as a social problem in Spain: Attitudes and
27 acceptability. *Sex Roles*, 70(11-12), 506-521. doi: 10.1007/s11199-013-0322-z
28
29
- 30 Ferrer, V. A., Bosch, E., Ramis, M. C., Torrans, G., & Navarro, C. (2006). La violencia contra las
31 mujeres en la pareja: creencias y actitudes en estudiantes universitarios/as. *Psicothema*,
32 18(3), 359-366.
33
34
35
- 36 Flood, M., & Pease, B. (2009). Factors influencing attitudes to violence against women. *Trauma*,
37 *Violence & Abuse*, 10, 125-142. doi: 10.1177/1524838009334131
38
39
40
- 41 FRA (European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights) (2014). *Violence against women: an EU-wide*
42 *Surrey. Main results*. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. Retrieved from:
43 http://fra.europa.eu/sites/default/files/fra-2014-vaw-survey-main-results_en.pdf
44
45
46
- 47 Fulu, E., Jewkes, R., & Garcia-Moreno, C. (2013). Prevalence of and factors associated with male
48 perpetration of intimate partner violence: findings from the UN multi-country cross-sectional
49 study on men and violence in Asia and the Pacific. *Lancet Global Health*, 1, e187–207. doi:
50 10.1016/S2214-109X(13)70074-3
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 Garcia-Moreno, C., Jansen, H. A., Ellsberg, M., Heise, L., & Watts, C. H. (2006). Prevalence of intimate
4 partner violence: findings from the WHO multi-country study on women's health and
5 domestic violence. *The Lancet*, *368*, 1260-1269.
6
7
8
- 9 Gawronski, B., & Bodenhausen, G. V. (2006). Associative and propositional processes in evaluation:
10 An integrative review of implicit and explicit attitude change. *Psychological Bulletin*, *132*(5),
11 692-731.
12
13
14
- 15 Glashouwer, K. A., Smulders, F. T., de Jong, P. J., Roefs, A., & Wiers, R. W. (2013). Measuring
16 automatic associations: Validation of algorithms for the Implicit Association Test (IAT) in a
17 laboratory setting. *Journal of Behavior Therapy and Experimental Psychiatry*, *44*, 105e-113.
18
19
20
- 21 Glasman, L. R., & Albarracín, D. (2006). Forming attitudes that predict future behavior: A meta-
22 analysis of the attitude-behavior relation. *Psychological Bulletin*, *132*(5), 778-822.
23
24
25
- 26 Gracia, E., & Lila, M. (2015). *Attitudes towards violence against women in the EU*. Luxembourg:
27 European Commission - Directorate-General for Justice.
28
29
- 30 Gracia, E., & Tomás, J. M. (2014). Correlates of victim-blaming attitudes regarding partner violence
31 against women among the Spanish general population. *Violence Against Women*, *20*(1) 26–41.
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
- 51 Greenwald, A. G., McGhee, D. E., & Schwartz, J. K. L. (1998). Measuring individual differences in
52 implicit cognition: The Implicit Association Test. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*,
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 Greenwald, A. G., Nosek, B. A., & Banaji, M. R. (2003). Understanding and Using the Implicit
4 Association Test: I. An improved scoring algorithm. *Journal of Personality and Social*
5 *Psychology, 85*(2), 197–216.
6
7
8
9 Greenwald, A. G., Poehlman, T. A., Uhlmann, E. L., & Banaji, M. R. (2009). Understanding and using
10 Implicit Association Test: III: Meta-analysis of predictive validity. *Journal of Personality and*
11 *Social Psychology, 97*, 17-41. doi: 10.1037/a0015575
12
13
14
15 Guilford, J. P. (1954). *Psychometric Methods*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
16
17
18 Harris, R. J., Firestone, J. M., & Vega, W. A. (2005). The interaction of country of origin, acculturation,
19 and gender role ideology on wife abuse. *Social Science Quarterly, 86*, 463-483. doi:
20 10.1111/j.0038-4941.2005.00313.x
21
22
23
24 Heise, L., & Kotsadam, A. (2015). Cross-national and multilevel correlates of partner violence: an
25 analysis of data from population-based surveys. *Lancet Global Health, 3*, e332–340. doi:
26 10.1016/S2214-109X(15)00013-3
27
28
29
30 Jewkes, R., Flood, M., & Lang, J. (2015). From work with men and boys to changes of social norms
31 and reduction of inequities in gender relations: a conceptual shift in prevention of violence
32 against women and girls. *The Lancet, 385*(9977), 1580-1589. doi: 10.1016/S0140-
33 6736(14)61683-4
34
35
36
37
38 Kingsnorth, R., & MacIntosh, R. (2004). Domestic violence: Predictors of victim support for official
39 action. *Justice Quarterly, 21*, 301-328. doi: 10.1080/07418820400095821
40
41
42
43 Larue, D., Schmidt, A. F., Imhoff, R., Eggers, K., Schönbrodt, F. D., & Banse, R. (2014). Validation of
44 direct and indirect measures of preference for sexualized violence. *Psychological Assessment,*
45 *26*(4), 1173–1183. doi: 10.1037/pas0000016
46
47
48
49 Lee, M.S., Begun, S., DePrince, A.P., & Chu, A.T. (2016). Acceptability of dating violence and
50 expectations of relationship harm among adolescent girls exposed to intimate partner
51 violence. *Psychological Trauma: Theory, Research, Practice, and Policy, 8*(4), 487-494. doi:
52 10.1037/tra0000130
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 Martin-Fernandez, M., Gracia, E., Marco, M., Vargas, V., Santirso, F. A., & Lila, M. (2018). Measuring
4
5 Acceptability of Intimate Partner Violence Against Women: Development and Validation of the
6
7 A-IPVAW Scale. *The European Journal of Psychology Applied to Legal Context*, *10*(1), 26-34.
8
9 doi: 10.5093/ejpalc2018a3
10
- 11 Mathôt, S., Schreij, D., & Theeuwes, J. (2012). OpenSesame: An open-source, graphical experiment
12
13 builder for the social sciences. *Behavior Research Methods*, *44*(2), 314-324. doi:
14
15 10.3758/s13428-011-0168-7
16
17
- 18 Nosek, B. A. (2005). Moderators of the relationship between implicit and explicit evaluation. *Journal*
19
20 *of Experimental Psychology: General*, *134*, 565–584.
21
- 22 Nosek, B. A., & Smyth, F. L. (2007). A multitrait-multimethod validation of the Implicit Association
23
24 Test: Implicit and explicit attitudes are related but distinct constructs. *Experimental*
25
26 *Psychology*, *54*(1), 14-29. doi: 10.1027/1618-3169.54.1.14
27
- 28 Nosek, B. A., Banaji, M. R., & Greenwald, A. G. (2002). Math = male, me = female, therefore math is
29
30 not equal to me. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *83*, 44-59. doi: 10.1037/0022-
31
32 3514.83.1.44
33
- 34 Nosek, B. A., Bar-Anan, Y., Sriram, N., Jordan, A., & Greenwald, A. G. (2014). Understanding and
35
36 Using the Brief Implicit Association Test: Recommended Scoring Procedures. *PLoS ONE*, *9*(12),
37
38 e110938. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0110938
39
- 40 Nosek, B. A., Greenwald, A. G., & Banaji, M. R. (2007). The Implicit Association Test at age 7: A
41
42 methodological and conceptual review. In J. A. Bargh (Ed.), *Automatic processes in social*
43
44 *thinking and behavior* (pp. 265-292). London: Psychology Press.
45
46
- 47 Olson, M. A., & Fazio, R. H. (2004). Reducing the influence of extra-personal associations on the
48
49 implicit association test: Personalizing the IAT. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*,
50
51 *86*, 653–667. doi: 10.1037/0022-3514.86.5.653
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 Olson, M. A., & Fazio, R. H. (2009). Implicit and explicit measures of attitudes: The perspective of the
4
5 MODE model. In R. E. Petty, R. H. Fazio, & P. Briñol (Eds.), *Attitudes: Insights from the new*
6
7 *implicit measures* (pp. 19-64). Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum.
- 8
9 *Organic Act 1/2004 on Integral Protection Measures against Gender Violence*. Boletín Oficial del
10
11 Estado núm. 313, 42166-42197.
- 12
13 Paulhus, D. L., & Vazire, S. (2007). The self-report method. In R. W. Robins, R. C. Fraley & R. F.
14
15 Krueger (Eds.), *Handbook of research methods in personality psychology*. (pp. 224-239). New
16
17 York, NY: Guilford Press.
- 18
19 Payne, B. K., & Gawronski, B. (2010). A history of implicit social cognition: Where is it coming from?
20
21 Where is it now? Where is it going? *Handbook of implicit social cognition: Measurement,*
22
23 *theory, and applications* (pp. 1-15). New York: Guilford Press.
- 24
25 Puente, A., Ubillos, S., Echeburua, E., & Paez, D. (2016). Risk factors associated with the violence
26
27 against women in couples: a review of meta-analysis and recent studies. *Anales de Psicología,*
28
29 *32(1)*, 295-306. doi: 10.6018/analesps.32.1.189161
- 30
31 Puleo, A. (2008). La violencia de género y el género de la violencia [Gender violence and the gender
32
33 of violence]. In A. Puleo (Ed.), *El reto de la igualdad de género. Nuevas perspectivas en ética y*
34
35 *filosofía política* [The challenge of gender equality. New perspectives on ethics and political
36
37 philosophy] (pp. 361-371). Madrid, Spain: Biblioteca Nueva.
- 38
39 Richetin, J., Costantini, G., Perugini, M., & Schönbrodt, F. (2015). Should we stop looking for a better
40
41 scoring algorithm for handling Implicit Association Test data? Test of the role of errors,
42
43 extreme latencies treatment, scoring formula, and practice trials on reliability and validity.
44
45 *PLoS ONE*, *10(6)*, e0129601. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0129601
- 46
47
48
49 Robertson, K., & Murachver, T. (2007). Correlates of partner violence for incarcerated women and
50
51 men. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, *22(5)*, 639-655. doi: 10.1177/0886260506298835.
- 52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

- 1
2
3 Rodriguez, P., & Khalil, H. (2017). Changing Values: Attitudes about Intimate Partner Violence in
4 Immigrants and Natives in Five Western Countries. *Deviant Behavior, 38*(3), 241-253. doi:
5 10.1080/01639625.2016.1196980
6
7
8
9 Ryan, K. M. (2013). Issues of reliability in measuring intimate partner violence during courtship. *Sex*
10 *Roles, 69*(3-4), 131-148. doi: 10.1007/s11199-012-0233-4
11
12
13 Saunders, D. G., Lynch, A. B., Grayson, M., & Linz, D. (1987). The Inventory of Beliefs about Wife
14 Beating: The construction and initial validation of a measure of beliefs and attitudes. *Violence*
15 *and Victims, 2*(1), 39-57.
16
17
18 Schmitt, N. (1996). Uses and abuses of Coefficient Alpha. *Psychological Assessment, 8*(4), 350-353.
19 doi: 10.1037/1040-3590.8.4.350
20
21
22
23 Scott, K., & Straus, M. (2007). Denial, minimization, partner blaming, and intimate aggression in
24 dating partners. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence, 22*(7), 851-871. doi:
25 10.1177/0886260507301227
26
27
28
29
30 Simane-Vigante, L., Plotka, I., & Blumenau, N. (2015). Research of attitudes towards criminal
31 violence with implicit and explicit measures of cognition. *Journal of Education, Psychology and*
32 *Social Sciences, 3*(2), 72-77.
33
34
35
36 Stockl, H., Devries, K., Rotstein, A., Abrahams, N., Campbell, J., Watts, C., & Garcia-Moreno, C.
37 (2013). The global prevalence of intimate partner homicide: a systematic review. *The Lancet,*
38 *382,* 859-865.
39
40
41
42
43 Süssenbach, P., Albrechet, S., & Bohner, G. (2017). Implicit judgements of rape cases: an experiment
44 on the determinants and consequences of implicit evaluations in a rape case. *Psychology,*
45 *Crime & Law, 23*(3), 291-304. doi: 10.1080/1068316X.2016.1247160
46
47
48
49 Uthman, O. A., Moradi, T., & Lawoko, S. (2010) The role of individual, community and societal
50 gender inequality in forming women's attitudes toward intimate-partner violence against
51 women: a multilevel analysis. *World Health & Population, 12*(2), 5-17.
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

1
2
3 Uthman, O. A., Moradi, T., & Lawoko, S. (2011). Are individual and community acceptance and
4
5 witnessing of intimate partner violence related to its occurrence? Multilevel structural
6
7 equation model. *PLoS ONE* 6(12):e27738. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0027738
8

9 Valor-Segura, I., Expósito, F., Moya, M., & López, K. (2014). Violence against women in Spain and
10
11 Cuba: the same reality, two different visions. *Revista de Psicología Social*, 29(1), 150-179. doi:
12
13 10.1080/02134748.2013.8785737
14

15 Waltermaurer, E. (2012). Public justification of intimate partner violence: a review of the literature.
16
17 *Trauma Violence Abuse*, 13, 167–175. doi: 1177/1524838012447699
18

19 Wang, L. (2016). Factors influencing attitude toward intimate partner violence. *Aggression & Violent*
20
21 *Behavior*, 29, 72-78. doi: 10.1016/j.avb.2016.06.005
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Table 1
Frequency distribution of IAT effects

IAT condition	Without-Feedback		With-Feedback	
	+600ms	+600ms	Built-in error penalty	
Null	5	2	2	
[$-.15 \leq D < .15$]	(5.0%)	(2.2%)	(2.2%)	
Mild	19	14	15	
[$.15 \leq D < .50$]	(18.8%)	(15.7%)	(16.9%)	
Moderate	22	39	40	
[$.50 \leq D < .80$]	(21.8%)	(43.8%)	(44.9%)	
Strong	55	34	32	
[$D \geq .80$]	(54.4%)	(38.2%)	(36.0%)	
Total	101 (100%)	89 (100%)	89 (100%)	

Table 2

Implicit and explicit measures of gender violence rejection (IBWB)

	Null	Mild	Moderate	Strong
Implicit measures GV-IAT	2	15	40	32
(n=89*)	(2.2%)	(16.9%)	(44.9%)	(36.0%)
1. Wife beating is justified	-	-	1	81
(IBWB-WJ) (n=82)			(1.1%)	(91.0%)
2. Wife gains from beating	-	1	5	82
(IBWB-WG) (n=88)		(1.1%)	(5.6%)	(92.1%)
3. Help should (not)** be given	2	4	10	72
(IBWB-HG) (n=88)	(2.2%)	(4.5%)	(11.2%)	(80.9%)
4. Offender should (not) ** be punished	3	5	3	77
(IBWB-OP) (n=88)	(3.4%)	(5.6%)	(3.4%)	(86.5%)
5. Offender is (not) ** responsible	-	16	33	36
(IBWB-OR) (n=85)		(18.0%)	(37.1%)	(40.4%)

* Only participants from the condition *with feedback* were included, and only D-scores obtained by the *built-in error penalty* algorithm were considered.

** The dimension is expressed in the opposite sense (*not helping, not punishing, not responsible...*)

Table 3

Implicit and explicit measures of gender violence rejection (IPDMV)

	Null	Mild	Moderate	Strong
Implicit measures GV-IAT (n=89*)	2 (2.2%)	15 (16.9%)	40 (44.9%)	32 (36.0%)
1. Inferiority_of_women_compared_to_men (IPDMV-IW) (n=89)	-	-	-	89 (100%)
2. Blaming_women_victims_of_abuse (IPDMV-BW) (n=85)	-	1 (1.1%)	14 (15.7%)	70 (78.8%)
3. Violence_as_problem-solving_strategy (IPDMV-VP) (n=89)	-	-	4 (4.5%)	85 (95.5%)
4. Minimization_and_exoneration_of_abuser (IPDMV-MA) (n=86)	10 (11.2%)	24 (27.0%)	26 (29.2%)	26 (29.2%)

* Only participants from the condition *with feedback* were included, and only D-scores obtained by the *built-in error penalty* algorithm were considered.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Table 4

Relation between Implicit and explicit measures of gender violence rejection (Chi Squared)

	Explicit measures: IBWB	Explicit measures: IPDMV
GV-IAT Effect	1. WJ: $\chi^2_{6df} = 6.851$ (p = 0.335)	1. IW: (All cases Strong Rejection)
(with feedback,	2. WG: $\chi^2_{6df} = 3.849$ (p = 0.697)	2. BW: $\chi^2_{6df} = 3.724$ (p = 0.714)
built-in error penalty	3. HG: $\chi^2_{9df} = 12.945$ (p = 0.165)	3. VP: $\chi^2_{6df} = 3.947$ (p = 0.684)
scores)	4. OP: $\chi^2_{9df} = 9.645$ (p = 0.380)	4. MA: $\chi^2_{9df} = 12.830$ (p = 0.170)
	5. OR: $\chi^2_{6df} = 6.401$ (p = 0.380)	

df = degrees of freedom

For Peer Review

Table 5

Comparison by sex, knowledge and activities (Mann-Whitney Test)

GV-IAT Effect	Sex	Knowledge	Extracurricular activities
(with feedback, built-in error penalty scores)	Men (n=10) Women (n=79)	Yes (n=53) No (n=36)	Yes (n=50) No (n=39)
1. Wife beating is justified (IBWB-WJ)	$U_{(M-W)} = 273.5$ $Z = -0.879$ $p = 0.380$	$U_{(M-W)} = 678.0$ $Z = -1.159$ $p = 0.247$	$U_{(M-W)} = 816.0$ $Z = -0.200$ $p = 0.841$
2. Wife gains from beating (IBWB-WG)	$U_{(M-W)} = 347.5$ $Z = -0.578$ $p = 0.564$	$U_{(M-W)} = 891.5$ $Z = -0.165$ $p = 0.869$	$U_{(M-W)} = 943.5$ $Z = -0.057$ $p = 0.955$
3. Help should (not) be given (IBWB-HG)	$U_{(M-W)} = 382.5$ $Z = -0.107$ $p = 0.915$	$U_{(M-W)} = 621.5$ $Z = -2.622$ $p = 0.009$	$U_{(M-W)} = 894.5$ $Z = -0.554$ $p = 0.3580$
4. Offender should (not)* be punished (IBWB-OP)	$U_{(M-W)} = 334.5$ $Z = -0.757$ $p = 0.449$	$U_{(M-W)} = 732.5$ $Z = -1.520$ $p = 0.128$	$U_{(M-W)} = 749.5$ $Z = -1.795$ $p = 0.073$
5. Offender is (not)* responsible (IBWB-OR)	$U_{(M-W)} = 326.0$ $Z = -0.678$ $p = 0.498$	$U_{(M-W)} = 676.0$ $Z = -1.457$ $p = 0.145$	$U_{(M-W)} = 870.0$ $Z = -0.206$ $p = 0.837$
1. Inferiority of women compared to men (IPDMV-IW)	$U_{(M-W)} = 364.0$ $Z = -0.705$ $p = 0.481$	$U_{(M-W)} = 902.5$ $Z = -0.371$ $p = 0.710$	$U_{(M-W)} = 939.0$ $Z = -0.521$ $p = 0.602$
2. Blaming women victims of abuse (IPDMV-BW)	$U_{(M-W)} = 291.0$ $Z = -1.160$ $p = 0.246$	$U_{(M-W)} = 742.0$ $Z = -0.997$ $p = 0.319$	$U_{(M-W)} = 864.5$ $Z = -0.158$ $p = 0.875$
3. Violence as problem solving strategy (IPDMV-VP)	$U_{(M-W)} = 356.0$ $Z = -0.516$ $p = 0.606$	$U_{(M-W)} = 713.0$ $Z = -1.862$ $p = 0.063$	$U_{(M-W)} = 883.0$ $Z = -0.775$ $p = 0.438$
4. Minimization and exoneration of abuser (IPDMV-MA)	$U_{(M-W)} = 345.0$ $Z = -0.476$ $p = 0.634$	$U_{(M-W)} = 784.5$ $Z = -0.748$ $p = 0.455$	$U_{(M-W)} = 3617.0$ $Z = -1.013$ $p = 0.311$

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60

Figure 1. Implicit rejection of gender violence in subjects with strong explicit rejection